

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for PARK9 (Q9NQ11) for use in western blot

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Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (1). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab259776	CVCL_0045	HEK293	WT
Abcam	ab274925	CVCL_B1AP	HEK293	<i>ATP13A2</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the PARK9 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab303528**	1006584-17	NA	recombinant mono	EPR26835-63	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Abcam	ab322735**	3101393855	NA	recombinant mono	MJF-D29756-28	rabbit	0.52	NA

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Working concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05

Figure 1: PARK9 antibody screening by western blot

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: PARK9 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HEK293 WT and *ATP13A2* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated PARK9 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab303528** at 1/1000 and ab322735** at 1/500. Predicted band size: 128.7 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.